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The conference will be organized in a HYBRID way, which will allow for both physical and online participation of the attendees.

The global economy of the twenty-first century has transformed the economic, social, and political landscape in a profound way. This century has been the scene of revolutions in information and communication technologies, enhanced economic integrations with capital mobility across readers, and a rapidly changing social environment.

In this context, **IRCOBESS 2024**'s main theme is "***New Approaches in Economics and Business: Problems & Opportunities***". In accordance with this, we welcome studies in the fields of economics and business management; also, in branches of social sciences such as public administration, politics, regional studies, and international studies that are related to economics and business management. Studies that are not within the scope of the conference will not be evaluated.

The aim of the conference is to gather leading academicians, policymakers, independent scholars, and researchers to share their knowledge, and new ideas as well as to discuss future development in these fields. It also provides a premier interdisciplinary platform for researchers, practitioners, and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns as well as practical challenges encountered and solutions adopted in the fields of Economics, Business, and Social Sciences.

An additional goal of the **IRCOBESS 2024** is to offer an opportunity for young researchers, academicians, and practitioners with multidisciplinary interests to meet and interact with members inside and outside their own particular disciplines.

WORK ON AN ETUDE MISE-EN-SCENE

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the role and importance of mise-en-scene in enhancing the expressiveness and spectacle of acting and directing etudes, emphasizing that each stage work should have its own mise-en-scene.

KEY WORDS

Etude, mise-en-scene, directing, actor, stage, performance, composition, behavior, confrontation, drama.

In the process of working on an etude, a well-founded mise-en-scene is important. As in a play, it is the most important effective means of revealing the thought and idea of the sketch. The importance of the mise-en-scene is even greater when we consider that in sketches there are no monologues or dialogues, and events are revealed mainly through behavior and circumstances.

Considering that an etude is a view of life that contains all the components of drama and has a compositional structure, it should be said that every etude should have its own mise-en-scene regardless of its type and appearance. Before we talk about etude scenery, let us understand what scenery is and what types of scenery there are. A mise-en-scene is a tool that enhances the expressiveness of a stage work and is used to inform the audience about the work. Mise en scene is derived from the French word "mise-en-scene", which means "a view of the stage". A mise-en-scene is created on the basis of the interaction of several elements of the stage, i.e. scenery, costumes, light, voice and behavior of the actors. It is the key to understanding and interpreting what is happening on stage.

It allows the director to create a certain situation, convey the idea of the play to the audience, highlight key moments and draw the audience's attention to the right situations. It also helps the actors to embody their characters and convey emotions to the audience.

Mise-en-scene is one of the main tools used by the director to convey to the audience what he wants to say in his production. That is why the famous director and teacher K.S. Stanislavsky describes "mise-en-scene is the director's language". A. Artaud, on the other hand, called mise-en-scene "the language of space and space on stage". "Mise-en-scene reflects the relationship between the participants, their behavior and struggle, the dynamic development of the action. Mise-en-scene is a plastic reflection of what is happening on stage, its beginning, development and end will depend on the development of the events taking place. It has a beginning, a development and an end, like a story.

One mise-en-scene passes into another as one event passes into another. It follows that a mise-en-scene in a play is a dynamic chain, inextricably linked, which plastically represents the action, rather than a single moment [1, P.60]. According to A.D.Popov, mise-en-scene is the most important means of communicating the director's idea to the viewer's feelings and thoughts. A mise-en-scene is a plastic and sound image that represents a person with a living behavior. Light, color, sound and music are supplementary, while word and movement are its main components. The written artistic image becomes the form of the mise-en-scene in the transition to the stage artistic image. A play is a pearl composed of mise-en-scene [2, P.13].

Therefore, *mise-en-scene* is the harmonious combination of all the components of his work reflected on the stage. It includes not only scenery, but also music, lighting and acting.

Mise-en-scene is an integral part of stagecraft and plays an important role in creating the atmosphere of the performance.

The main idea of *mise-en-scene* is to create a realistic stage background on the stage. The image of a real space is created by placing various decorations, objects and other elements. The director can use *mise-en-scene* not only to create a realistic atmosphere, but also to divide the scene into different sections. With a properly chosen *mise-en-scene* on the stage, it was possible to change time and space quickly and to move easily from one scene to another.

As the technical capabilities of the theatre improved, a variety of complex forms of *mise-en-scene* emerged. The expressiveness of *mise-en-scene* increased with the advent of mechanisms for rapid scene changes by dividing the stage into several parts using different lighting effects.

A *mise-en-scene* can include various elements and can be used to emphasize the main events taking place on stage or to draw the audience's attention to certain details of the scene. In theatre, the main purpose of a *mise-en-scene* is to enhance the effect of conveying to the audience what is happening on stage and to bring them into the world of the play.

The main thing is to work with the actors to create the overall atmosphere and support the theme and mood of the play. The set can vary according to the plot and interpretation of the play. It can be concrete, detailed or abstract, symbolic and created with a minimum of elements to convey certain ideas or feelings.

Each element of the *mise-en-scene* plays an important role in creating the image and atmosphere on stage. *Mise-en-scene* requires the ability to convey information through visual and symbolic means, to interact with the performance of the actors and the plot of the play. One aspect to consider when constructing a *mise-en-scene* is to ensure that the main event and action on stage is emphasized in a way that is understandable to the audience. Various techniques can be used to interact with the main event and action.

For example, they can make repetitive movements or gestures, react emotionally to what is happening, or create different sound effects.

In this way, the performers on stage, the set and the props become a single ensemble and help to create a single, coherent *mise-en-scene*. Scenery, props play an important role in the creation of the *mise-en-scene*; they can be used by the actors to achieve certain goals and create certain effects.

Lighting and special effects are also important in creating a *mise-en-scene*. They allow you to emphasize certain moments or create a certain atmosphere on stage. Lighting can be bright or dim. *Mise-en-scene* refers to all the elements that are present on the stage and created for the movement of the actors. The right *mise-en-scene*, set, costumes, lighting and sound help the audience to understand what is happening on stage and to feel the emotions of the actors.

In addition, *mise-en-scene* can be used to emphasize certain thoughts or ideas in a play. For example, various unusual *mise-en-scènes* can be used to convey to the audience the key points or symbolism of certain scenes.

Thus, *mise-en-scene* plays an important role in creating the atmosphere on stage and helps the audience to understand more deeply the thoughts and ideas presented in the play. It makes the quality of the set and the emotions of the actors more memorable and effective.

So even when staging *études*, one should take the *mise-en-scene* seriously. Working on the *mise-en-scene* of an *étude* is considered quite challenging for a student director. The teacher should provide the desired reference and direction. The process is as follows The student begins to work independently on the *étude* after the director has approved the *étude* script.

The student creates an *étude* *mise-en-scene* based on the theoretical and practical knowledge that the director has mastered so far. The created *mise-en-scene* can be corrected, changed and some additions can be made by the teacher. During the work, the teacher gives explanations to the student. Any movement on stage cannot be called *mise-en-scene*. For *mise-en-scene* also has its own rules.

What determines the correctness of a mise-en-scene is its monasticism in relation to the reality of life and the mobility of the mise-en-scene.

The director must give the actor a purposeful mise-en-scene. In a given mise-en-scene, the actor cannot stand without moving. That is, there must be a force that makes it move by itself. In the performance itself, there must be a distinct line of physical movement for each participant. Excessive movement on the stage is unacceptable [3, P.284.] says Professor J.A. Mamatkosimov in his book *Acting*.

Serious attention should be paid to the mise-en-scene, as the etudes do not use dialogue. The mise-en-scene in the etudes should be interesting and truthful. Students think of mise-en-scene as a constant movement on stage during the work, a frequent change of circumstances. This is not the case.

Every step, every movement made on the stage must be directed towards a specific goal. Every action performed by the player must be free of various minor miracles and trivialities. Otherwise, the stage value of the action will decrease.

The director must place the actor in such a way that he can respond to the general idea of the play and organise the composition of the play. Let the actor think about the correctness of the director's idea for this work, understand it, know his task well - then the actor will confidently take his place in stage life. Create a real mise-en-scene, stage action.

There are two ways of creating a mise-en-scene, depending on the skill and experience of the director. In the first style, the director creates a deliberate mise-en-scene based on the theme, idea and higher purpose of the play. This technique helps to expressively interpret the director's purpose. In the second style, the mise-en-scene is usually conceived in collaboration with the actors during the performance. In this method, the story and character of the characters as they progress through the play are important.

This means that a production, no matter how big or small, must have its exact and correctly found mise-en-scene. This rule also applies to etudes. Etudes in the process of performance should serve to convey to the audience the mise-en-scene, the outer and inner state of the performers, and express their behaviour and appearance.

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